

Supporting Information

Development of a biodegradable green emitter chitosan-based OLED for implantable biomedical devices

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The PDF file includes:

Figs. S1 to S8

Other Supplementary Materials for this manuscript include the following:

Movies S1 to S2

Figure S1. A) Setup scheme used to follow the degradation of the AlQ₃ film upon contact with PBS. The film is positioned in such a way that it is out of the excitation beam trajectory. B) Photos of a 140 nm thick film of AlQ₃ on glass and of the glass that remained after the experiment of Figure S1A, under illumination at 254 nm. C) Absorption spectra of a film of AlQ₃ on glass, after being immersed in PBS for 4 days and then after rinsing with water (release of some degradation products that remained precipitated on the glass substrate).

Figure S2. Transmittance of ITO/PEDOT (red line) vs Mg/MoO₃ (black line) both on glass substrates.

Figure S3. AFM 2D and 3D topography (a, b) images and corresponding phase image (c) of chitosan substrate (scan area is $2 \mu\text{m} \times 2 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure S4. UV–visible transmission spectrum of a chitosan substrate before (black line) and after (blue line) magnesium-based anode formation.

Figure S5. Structure of the OLEDs (A to C) and energy level diagram of the various components (D).

Figure S6. EL eff of the LEDs whose characteristics are shown in Figure 4.

Figure S7. Degradation of chitosan-based OLED immersed in PBS + 1mg/mL lysozyme solution. Absorbance measurements on the PBS + lysozyme solution reveal a decrease in the intensity of characteristic lysozyme bands, indicating its active role in degrading the chitosan-based OLED over time.

a.

b.

Figure S8. PLGA encapsulation of the chitosan-based OLED (a) improves the barrier against both oxygen and moisture, enabling the magnesium-based electrodes to remain stable for up to five months when stored outside of a glove box (b).

Movie S1.

Movie S1. After 24h of immersion, the degradation of chitosan-based OLED in PBS is limited, as the polymer curled and exhibited poor dissolution.

Movie S2.

Movie S2. In the presence of lysozyme, the chitosan-based OLED undergoes complete dissolution within 24 hours, driven by the enzymatic hydrolysis.